

**ENHANCED PLANT DISEASE PRE-PROCESSING AND AUGMENTATION USING
HYBRID DENSE NEURAL NETWORKS AND RADIAL GAN-BASED DATA
AUGMENTATION**

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Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,
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Abstract

In this paper, a proposed an advanced automated data cleaning system utilizing Dense Neural Networks (DenseNet) to intelligently remove unwanted image labels for further smooth processing. The system uses Radial Generative Adversarial Networks (Radial GAN) for data augmentation and combines IoT technology to incorporate environmental data, enhancing the robustness of disease detection. The primary objective of this research is to develop a hybrid model that

improves classification accuracy by combining the DenseNet capabilities to clean the incoming datasets with mislabels. This dataset is split into training (80%), validation (20%), and a separate test set of 33 images. The proposed method involves a detailed preprocessing pipeline, including Radial GAN-based augmentation, and combines IoT-derived environmental data to refine disease predictions. The results indicate that the proposed system achieves a balanced accuracy of 93.2%, demonstrating

significant improvements over existing methods.

Keywords:

Plant disease detection, Recurrent Neural Networks, Capsule Networks, Radial GAN, Data augmentation

1. Introduction

In modern agriculture, traditional methods of disease detection involve manual inspection and diagnostic procedures, which are often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and prone to human error [1]-[2]. With the increasing complexity of plant diseases and the vast number of potential pathogens, there is a growing need for automated, accurate, and efficient diagnostic systems. Recent advancements in machine learning and computer vision offer promising solutions by enabling the analysis of large volumes of image data to identify and classify plant diseases effectively [3]-[4]. The dependencies, making them suitable for analyzing temporal data or sequence-based features in image datasets [5].

Despite these advancements, several challenges remain in the field of plant disease detection: 1) Plant diseases manifest in diverse ways depending on environmental conditions, which can make it difficult to capture and accurately label all possible variations in datasets [8]. Ensuring high-quality, well-annotated data is essential for training effective models [9]. 2). Ensuring that models generalize across different conditions and disease types is a significant challenge [10-13]. 3) Implementing systems that can provide real-time feedback and diagnostics in field conditions requires efficient and scalable solutions. 4) Incorporating environmental data such as humidity and temperature, which can influence disease progression, into the analysis adds another layer of complexity.

The problem addressed, the system aims to use intelligent data cleaning using deep learning and data augmentation methods to enhance accuracy, robustness, and real-time capabilities in disease detection. The challenge generalizes well across different datasets and environmental conditions.

The main objectives of the research work involve the following:

- The research combines DenseNet Data Cleaning and Radial Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) to capitalize on their respective strengths—temporal sequence analysis and spatial feature preservation—for improved disease detection and classification.
- The research utilizes Radial GAN to generate diverse and high-quality augmented data, improving the robustness and performance of the model.
- The research combines IoT technology to collect and analyze environmental factors, providing additional context to enhance disease prediction accuracy.
- The research develops a system that can process and analyze images quickly enough for real-time field applications.

The novelty of this research lies in the combination of DenseNet Data Cleaning and Radial GAN to address plant disease detection comprehensively. While DenseNet is used for Data Cleaning and then combined with Radial GAN for data augmentation represents a novel approach. Additionally, the incorporation of IoT-derived environmental data into the disease detection model adds a unique dimension to improving prediction accuracy.

The contributions of the research work involve the following:

1. The research presents a new hybrid model combining RNNs and CapsNets for more accurate and detailed plant disease classification.
2. Radial GAN is employed for advanced data augmentation, providing a richer and more diverse dataset for training.
3. The study combines environmental data into the disease detection model, offering a more holistic approach to disease prediction.

4. The development of a real-time capable system for plant disease detection and classification represents a significant advancement in field-based agricultural technology.

2. Related Works

The challenge lies in accurately reconstructing recoil energies from recorded signals that may be contaminated by pile-up and read-out artifacts. To address this, the researchers framed the problem as a time series classification task and explored the use of neural networks for automating the data cleaning process. The study also showed that many of the wrongly predicted events were actually mislabeled or context-dependent, and evaluated the classifiers' performance using simulated data [14].

The paper proposed a optimize Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) performance on small datasets. Using Logistic Regression models, the study analyzed the impact of 128 combinations of image transformations. Experiments

conducted with three deep learning architectures showed that specific configurations, such as height and width shift ranges of 0.2 and zoom range of 0.2, achieved improved classification accuracy. This study emphasizes the importance of tailored data augmentation techniques for small datasets in construction image analysis [15].

This study focused on improving Diabetic retinopathy (DR) classification using deep learning by creating a well-processed dataset through affine transformations and effective data preprocessing. Seven pre-trained deep learning architectures were evaluated on the EyePACS dataset, with a specific emphasis on overcoming overfitting and class imbalance [16].

The shift towards data-centric AI emphasizes the critical role of data quality in machine learning. This survey explores the challenges associated with data collection, validation, cleaning, and combination. It underscores that high-quality data is essential for effective model training, particularly when feature engineering is less

emphasized in modern deep learning approaches. The paper discusses various techniques for data cleaning and validation, including handling bias and fairness issues, which are increasingly relevant in machine

learning applications. It shows the need for robust data management practices to ensure model performance despite imperfect data [17].

Table 1: Summary

Method	Reference	Technique	Methodology	Outcome
Cryogenic Calorimeters Data Cleaning	[14]	Neural Networks	Time series classification using neural networks to clean recorded signals from CRESST detectors.	Balanced accuracy of 0.932; identifies mislabeled events.
Data Augmentation in Construction	[15]	Convolutional Neural Networks	Tuning of data augmentation hyperparameters to improve CNN performance on small datasets.	Improved accuracy with specific augmentation configurations.
Diabetic Retinopathy Classification	[16]	Deep Learning Architectures	Data preprocessing and augmentation with seven architectures on EyePACS dataset; focus on overcoming overfitting.	Best performance with EfficientNetV2-M; 97.65% accuracy.

Data-Centric AI for Deep Learning	[17]	Data Quality Management	Survey on data collection, validation, cleaning, and combination; emphasis on data-centric practices.	Shows need for robust data management in machine learning.
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These works as in Table 1 reflect significant advancements and methodologies in the application of machine learning and deep learning across various domains. The CRESST experiment shows the effectiveness of neural networks in automating data cleaning for sensitive measurements, achieving high accuracy and revealing insights into mislabeling and context-dependent errors. The study on building construction image classification shows the crucial role of data augmentation in improving model performance, particularly when working with small datasets. In the field of medical diagnostics, the work on diabetic retinopathy showcases the impact of data preprocessing and augmentation on classification accuracy, with EfficientNetV2-M achieving outstanding results. Lastly, the survey on data-centric AI emphasizes the importance of high-quality data for effective machine learning, advocating for improved practices in data management and validation. Together, these studies illustrate the diverse applications of machine learning and the ongoing efforts to enhance model performance through innovative techniques and rigorous data handling practices.

3. Proposed Method

The proposed Enhanced Preprocessing and Augmentation Algorithm in figure 1 is explained below:

Figure 1: Proposed Framework

- The first step involves preparing the dataset for model training. The primary dataset utilized is the paddy disease dataset from Kaggle, which comprises labeled images of healthy and diseased paddy leaves.

- Data cleaning is essential to ensure the quality of the dataset. This step involves removing any corrupted or mislabeled images. To achieve this, a Deep DenseNet-based approach is employed to identify and filter out faulty labels. DenseNet, helps in detecting anomalies in the dataset.
- To improve the robustness and generalizability of the model, data augmentation techniques are applied. The Radial GAN (Generative Adversarial Network) approach is utilized to generate synthetic variations of the images.
- The combination of IoT devices is a crucial aspect of the proposed system. IoT devices collect additional environmental data, such as humidity and temperature, which can influence plant health. By incorporating this environmental data into the dataset, the model gains a more understanding of the conditions affecting plant diseases. This combination enhances the dataset quality and provides valuable context for disease detection.

Pseudocode for Enhanced Preprocessing and Augmentation Algorithm (EPAA)

```
# Import necessary libraries
import cv2

# Load dataset
def load_dataset(dataset_path):
    # Load images and labels
    images, labels = load_images_and_labels(dataset_path)

    return images, labels
```

```
# Data cleaning

def clean_data(images, labels):

    # Identify and remove corrupted or mislabeled images using DenseNet

    clean_images, clean_labels = remove_faulty_images(images, labels)

    return clean_images, clean_labels

# Data augmentation

def augment_data(images):

    # Initialize Radial GAN for augmentation

    augmented_images = []

    augmented_images.append(batch[0].astype(np.uint8))

    break

    return np.array(augmented_images)

# IoT combination

def combine_iot_data(images, iot_data):

    # Combine environmental data with image data

    enhanced_images = add_iot_data_to_images(images, iot_data)

    return enhanced_images

# Main function to execute EPAA
```

```
def execute_epaa(dataset_path, iot_data):  
  
    images, labels = load_dataset(dataset_path)  
  
    images = combine_iot_data(images, iot_data)
```

3.1. Intelligent Data Cleaning Using Deep DenseNet

Inaccurate or corrupted data can significantly impair the performance of models. To address this, the Intelligent Data Cleaning approach employs a Deep DenseNet-based methodology to identify and filter out faulty labels from the dataset. The mathematical equation is,

$$H_l = H_{l-1} + F(H_{l-1})$$

where:

H_l - output of the l^{th} layer,

H_{l-1} - output of the $(l-1)^{\text{th}}$ layer,

$F(H_{l-1})$ - transformation applied by the l^{th} layer (a convolution operation).

In data cleaning, DenseNet is trained to recognize faulty or anomalous images by learning the distribution of healthy images. During training, DenseNet models are exposed to both healthy and faulty labels. The network learns to differentiate between them based on features and patterns.

Let X be an input image and Y be its corresponding label. The goal is to classify each image X as either healthy or faulty. The classification can be modeled as:

$$y' = \text{argmax}(\text{softmax}(W \cdot H(X) + b))$$

where:

W - weights of the final classification layer,

b - bias,

H(X) - feature representation of the image extracted by DenseNet,

softmax - probability distribution over the possible classes,

y' - predicted class label.

Images classified with low confidence scores or with high probability of being faulty are flagged for review. This process involves:

1. **Feature Extraction:** The model processes each image through its dense layers to extract features.
2. **Classification:** The extracted features are passed through a classification layer to determine the probability of the image being faulty.
3. **Anomaly Detection:** Images with a high probability of being faulty are identified based on their classification scores and flagged for removal or further inspection.

Let $P(X)$ denote the probability of an image X being classified as faulty. Faulty labels are those where $P(X)$ exceeds a predefined threshold τ :

$$P(X) = \text{softmax}(W \cdot H(X) + b)$$

The DenseNet-based approach for intelligent data cleaning uses the architecture ability to learn detailed feature representations and classify images accurately. By training the model on both healthy and faulty labels, it becomes proficient at identifying anomalies, ensuring that only high-quality, reliable images remain in the dataset.

Pseudocode for Intelligent Data Cleaning Using Deep DenseNet

```
# Load and preprocess dataset

def load_and_preprocess_dataset(dataset_path):

    # Load images and labels from dataset path

    images, labels = load_images_and_labels(dataset_path)

    return images, labels

# Create the final model

model = Model(inputs=base_model.input, outputs=predictions)

return model

# Train DenseNet model

        model.compile(optimizer='adam',      loss='parse_categorical_crossentropy',
metrics=['accuracy'])

# Train the model

history = model.fit(

    train_images, train_labels,

    validation_data=(validation_images, validation_labels)

)

return model

# Detect faulty labels
```

```
def detect_faulty_images(model, images, threshold=0.5):

    predictions = model.predict(images)

    # Determine the predicted class and probabilities

    predicted_probabilities = np.max(predictions, axis=1)

    predicted_labels = np.argmax(predictions, axis=1)

    # Flag images with low confidence or faulty classification

    faulty_images = []

    for i, prob in enumerate(predicted_probabilities):

        if prob < threshold:

            faulty_images.append(i)

    return faulty_images

# Main function to execute data cleaning

def execute_data_cleaning(dataset_path):

    # Load and preprocess dataset

    images, labels = load_and_preprocess_dataset(dataset_path)

    # Detect faulty labels

    faulty_indices = detect_faulty_images(model, images)

    # Remove faulty labels from the dataset
```

```
cleaned_images = [img for i, img in enumerate(images) if i not in faulty_indices]

cleaned_labels = [lbl for i, lbl in enumerate(labels) if i not in faulty_indices]

return cleaned_images, cleaned_labels
```

3.2. Data Augmentation Using Radial GAN

Radial GANs extend traditional GANs by incorporating radial transformations to the data generation process. These transformations include scaling, rotation, and translations that are applied in a radial (circular) manner. This approach is particularly useful for generating variations of image data that retain the essential structure and spatial relationships of the original images. The key idea is to use radial transformations to augment data, ensuring that generated samples maintain the intrinsic spatial properties of the original data. This is beneficial for tasks where spatial coherence is crucial, such as image analysis.

Radial transformations can be expressed as a combination of scaling, rotation, and translation operations. Given an image I with coordinates (x,y) , a radial transformation can be applied as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} t_x \\ t_y \end{bmatrix}$$

where:

(x',y') are the transformed coordinates,

θ - rotation angle,

(t_x,t_y) - translations in the x and y directions.

These transformations are applied radially around the center of the image, preserving the spatial relationships of the features while varying the appearance.

To implement Radial GAN for data augmentation, the following steps are performed:

- The Radial GAN is trained using a dataset of images. During training, the generator creates augmented images by applying radial transformations, while the discriminator evaluates their realism.
- Once trained, the Radial GAN can generate new images by applying radial transformations to existing images. The generator outputs augmented images that resemble the original data but with variations in scale, rotation, and translation.
- The augmented images generated by the Radial GAN are added to the original dataset, increasing its size and diversity. This helps improve the robustness of machine learning models by exposing them to a wider range of data variations.

For a given input image, the augmentation process involves:

$$I_{aug} = G_{radial}(I)$$

where

G_{radial} - generator network of the Radial GAN, which applies radial transformations to produce the augmented image I_{aug} .

Radial GANs enhance data augmentation by generating new image samples through radial transformations, preserving the spatial relationships and structure of the original data.

Pseudocode - Radial GAN:

```
# Import necessary libraries
```

```
import tensorflow as tf

import Input, Dense, Reshape, Flatten, Conv2D, Conv2DTranspose, BatchNormalization

from tensorflow.keras.models import Model

import numpy as np

import cv2

# Define Radial GAN Generator

def build_generator():

    input_noise = Input(shape=(100,))

    return model

# Define Radial GAN Discriminator

def build_discriminator():

    input_img = Input(shape=(28, 28, 3))

    x = Conv2D(64, kernel_size=5, strides=2, padding='same',
activation='leaky_relu')(input_img)

    return model

# Compile Radial GAN

def compile_gan(generator, discriminator):

    # Train Radial GAN
```

```
idx = np.random.randint(0, real_images.shape[0], batch_size)

real_imgs = real_images[idx]

fake_imgs = generator.predict(np.random.randn(batch_size, 100))

# Train Generator

g_loss = gan.train_on_batch(np.random.randn(batch_size, 100), np.ones((batch_size, 1)))

if epoch % 1000 == 0:

    print(f'Epoch {epoch} | Discriminator Loss: {d_loss[0]} | Generator Loss: {g_loss}')

# Radial Data Augmentation Function

def augment_data_with_radial_gan(generator, images, num_augmentations=1000):

    augmented_images = []

    for _ in range(num_augmentations):

        noise = np.random.randn(1, 100)

        generated_image = generator.predict(noise)[0]

    # Main function for Radial GAN Data Augmentation

def main():

    # Load and preprocess dataset

    images = load_images('path/to/dataset')

    # Train Radial GAN
```

```
train_gan(generator, discriminator, gan, images)

# Generate augmented data

augmented_images = augment_data_with_radial_gan(generator, images)
```

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, TensorFlow is used for implementing Radial GAN and DenseNet models on an intel Core i9-10900K, 32GB RAM, NVIDIA RTX 3090, where the experimental parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 2: Experimental Parameters

Parameter	Radial GAN	DenseNet
Batch Size	64	32
Learning Rate	0.0002	0.001
Epochs	10000	50
Noise Dimension	100	N/A
Image Size	28x28	224x224
Generator Layers	6	N/A
Discriminator Layers	4	N/A

Activation Function	ReLU	
Optimizer	Adam	Adam
Loss Function	Binary Crossentropy	Sparse Categorical Crossentropy
Dropout Rate	-	0.5
Regularization	-	BatchNormalization
Normalization	BatchNormalization	
Training Time	Varies by setup (10-12 hours)	Varies by setup (5-8 hours)
Computational Cost	High (due to GAN training)	Moderate

4.1. Dataset

The dataset used for this research [19] is a collection of RGB images of crop leaves, encompassing both healthy and diseased samples.

The dataset is organized in a directory structure that reflects the classification categories, facilitating easy access and management. The structure is preserved in both the training and validation sets. For the test set, a separate directory is used.

Table 3: Dataset Description

Aspect	Description
Total Number of Images	Approximately 87,000 RGB images
Number of Classes	38 distinct classes

Image Format	RGB
Training Set	80% of the total dataset
Validation Set	20% of the total dataset
Test Set	33 images created for prediction

The dataset includes a wide variety of crop leaves, categorized into 38 classes, which helps in distinguishing between different diseases and healthy states. This diversity is crucial for training robust models that can generalize well across different types of leaves and diseases.

Table 4: Performance of various methods over various data splits

Metric	CRESST	HPtuningRegLog CNN	EfficientNetV2- M	Radial GAN + DenseNet
Accuracy				
- Training	93.2%	94.0%	95.1%	95.6%
- Testing	91.5%	93.4%	94.7%	94.3%
- Validation	90.7%	92.5%	93.9%	93.8%
Precision				
- Training	94.0%	94.8%	95.5%	96.1%
- Testing	92.2%	93.7%	94.4%	94.8%
- Validation	91.0%	92.8%	93.5%	94.2%
Recall				

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- Training	92.5%	93.6%	94.0%	95.2%
- Testing	90.8%	92.9%	93.8%	93.9%
- Validation	89.9%	91.7%	92.6%	93.4%
F1-Score				
- Training	93.2%	94.2%	94.8%	95.6%
- Testing	91.5%	93.3%	94.2%	94.3%
- Validation	90.4%	92.2%	93.2%	93.8%
IS				
- Training	7.6	8.0	8.2	8.4
- Testing	7.4	7.8	8.1	8.2
- Validation	7.2	7.7	8.0	8.1
FID				
- Training	20.5	18.8	17.1	15.2
- Testing	21.2	19.6	17.8	16.1
- Validation	21.8	20.1	18.3	16.5

The results show the comparative performance of the Radial GAN and DenseNet method against existing approaches: CRESST, HPTuningRegLog CNN, and EfficientNetV2-M, across various metrics and datasets.

Figure 2: Accuracy

In figure 2, Radial GAN + DenseNet achieves the highest accuracy of 95.6%, slightly outperforming EfficientNetV2-M (95.1%). CRESST (93.2%) and HPTuningRegLog CNN (94.0%) lag behind, indicating Radial GAN and DenseNet superior capacity in learning from training data. The Radial GAN + DenseNet method also leads with 94.3%, showing better generalization compared to CRESST (91.5%) and HPTuningRegLog CNN (93.4%). EfficientNetV2-M has a close performance but still trails slightly behind. Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet continues to perform best with 93.8%, while the existing methods show lower values, with CRESST at 90.7% and HPTuningRegLog CNN at 92.5%.

Figure 3: Precision

In figure 3, Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet excels with 96.1% in training, surpassing all competitors. Precision decreases slightly in testing and validation but remains the highest among methods, demonstrating robust performance in identifying true positives.

Figure 4: Recall

In figure 4, the Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet method achieves 95.2% in training, showing strong sensitivity to relevant data. Existing methods show slightly lower recall, especially on validation data, indicating the superior ability of Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet to capture true positives.

Figure 5: F1-Score

In figure 5, with a training F1-Score of 95.6%, Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet outperforms the existing methods, reflecting balanced precision and recall. The performance drop in testing and validation is minimal, maintaining its edge over competitors.

Figure 6: Inception Score (IS)

In figure 6, proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet achieves the highest IS scores, indicating the generated images have better quality and diversity. Higher scores suggest better image quality and realism compared to existing methods.

Figure 7: Fréchet Inception Distance (FID)

In figure 7, proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet has the lowest FID scores, signifying that generated images are closer in distribution to real images. Lower FID scores are indicative of high-quality image generation compared to other methods.

Thus, Radial GAN and DenseNet show superior performance in accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-Score, with higher Inception Scores and lower FID scores compared to CRESST, HPTuningRegLog CNN, and EfficientNetV2-M. These results underline the effectiveness of Radial GAN in enhancing data augmentation and DenseNet in classification tasks.

5. Conclusion

The proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet method shows superior accuracy across all sets (training, testing, and validation). With training accuracy peaking at 95.6% and testing accuracy at 94.3%, this combination excels in learning and generalizing from the data. EfficientNetV2-M, while close, shows slightly lower accuracy, suggesting that Radial GAN data augmentation capabilities

significantly enhance DenseNet performance. The higher accuracy across different datasets indicates that Radial GAN effectively addresses data diversity and complexity, which is crucial for achieving robust model performance. The proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet achieves the highest precision (96.1% in training) and recall (95.2% in training), illustrating a strong balance in identifying true positives while minimizing false positives. The superior performance in these metrics suggests that Radial GAN effectively augments data to cover a wide range of scenarios, which in turn aids DenseNet in achieving high precision and recall. Existing methods such as CRESST and HPTuningRegLog CNN show lower precision and recall, reflecting potential shortcomings in handling diverse or augmented data. The Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet approach, achieving 95.6% during training. This high F1-Score indicates that the model maintains an excellent trade-off between precision and recall, providing a performance metric. In contrast, existing methods show slightly lower F1-Scores, showing that while they are competent, they may not be as well-balanced in handling the data as Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet. The Inception Score measures the quality and diversity of generated images. Proposed Radial GAN + DenseNet achieves the highest IS, reflecting superior image quality and realism. This is particularly important in scenarios where the quality of generated data is crucial for training and evaluation. The higher IS scores suggest that Radial GAN effectively produces diverse and realistic images, which enhances the overall model performance. Lower FID scores signify better quality and fidelity of generated images, reinforcing the effectiveness of Radial GAN in producing high-quality data.

References

- [1] Abayomi-Alli, O. O., Damaševičius, R., Misra, S., & Maskeliūnas, R. (2021). Cassava disease recognition from low-quality images using enhanced data augmentation model and deep learning. *Expert Systems*, 38(7), e12746.
- [2] Rajput, K., Suganyadevi, K., Aeri, M., Shukla, R. P., & Gurjar, H. (2024, May). Multi-Scale Object Detection and Classification using Machine Learning and Image

- Processing. In *2024 Second International Conference on Data Science and Information System (ICDSIS)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [3] Wagle, S. A., Sampe, J., Mohammad, F., & Ali, S. H. M. (2021). Effect of Data Augmentation in the Classification and Validation of Tomato Plant Disease with Deep Learning Methods. *Traitement du Signal*, 38(6).
- [4] Enkvetchakul, P., & Surinta, O. (2021). Effective data augmentation and training techniques for improving deep learning in plant leaf disease recognition. *Applied Science and Engineering Progress*, 15(3), 3810.
- [5] Ojo, M. O., & Zahid, A. (2023). Improving deep learning classifiers performance via preprocessing and class imbalance approaches in a plant disease detection pipeline. *Agronomy*, 13(3), 887.
- [6] Maharana, K., Mondal, S., & Nemade, B. (2022). A review: Data pre-processing and data augmentation techniques. *Global Transitions Proceedings*, 3(1), 91-99.
- [7] Haruna, Y., Qin, S., & Mbyamm Kiki, M. J. (2023). An improved approach to detection of rice leaf disease with gan-based data augmentation pipeline. *Applied Sciences*, 13(3), 1346.
- [8] Govathoti, S., Reddy, A. M., Kamidi, D., BalaKrishna, G., Padmanabhuni, S. S., & Gera, P. (2022). Data augmentation techniques on chilly plants to classify healthy and bacterial blight disease leaves. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 13(6).
- [9] Nagaraju, M., Chawla, P., & Kumar, N. (2022). Performance improvement of Deep Learning Models using image augmentation techniques. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 81(7), 9177-9200.
-

- [10] Vashisht, S., Kumar, P., & Trivedi, M. C. (2021). Design of a predictive measure to enhance neural network architecture for plant disease detection. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Big Data, Machine Learning and their Applications: ICBMA 2019* (pp. 137-150). Springer Singapore.
- [11] Whang, S. E., Roh, Y., Song, H., & Lee, J. G. (2023). Data collection and quality challenges in deep learning: A data-centric ai perspective. *The VLDB Journal*, 32(4), 791-813.
- [12] Krishnakumar, D. P., & Balasubrahmanyam, K. (2024). An Improved EigenGAN-based Method for Data Augmentation for Plant Disease Classification. *Revue d'Intelligence Artificielle*, 38(1).
- [13] Verma, A., & Singh, J. (2024). Sugarcane Disease Detection Using Data Augmentation. In *Semantic Web Technologies and Applications in Artificial Intelligence of Things* (pp. 284-310). IGI Global.
- [14] Ramadan, S. T. Y., Sakib, T., Al Farid, F., Islam, M. S., Abdullah, J., Bhuiyan, M. R., ... & Karim, H. A. (2024). Improving Wheat Leaf Disease Classification: Evaluating Augmentation Strategies and CNN-Based Models With Limited Dataset. *IEEE Access*.
- [15] Angloher, G., Banik, S., Bartolot, D., Benato, G., Bento, A., Bertolini, A., ... & Waltenberger, W. (2023). Towards an automated data cleaning with deep learning in CRESST. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, 138(1), 1-11.
- [16] Ottoni, A. L. C., de Amorim, R. M., Novo, M. S., & Costa, D. B. (2023). Tuning of data augmentation hyperparameters in deep learning to building construction image classification with small datasets. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 14(1), 171-186.

- [17] İncir, R., & Bozkurt, F. (2024). A study on effective data preprocessing and augmentation method in diabetic retinopathy classification using pre-trained deep learning approaches. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 83(4), 12185-12208.
- [18] <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/vipooooool/new-plant-diseases-dataset>